

Scatterer Size Estimation with Fractal Analysis of Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) Images

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ABSTRACT

Accurate and robust estimation the scatterer size from Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) images has the potential to provide a diagnostically useful biomarker of disease. In the past, Mie Theory with curve fitting, the autocorrelation of the spectrum and the bandwidth of the correlation of the derivative (COD) have been explored for this purpose. However, these approaches are very challenging to apply to scatterer sizes below 4 μm due to their inherent lack of accuracy or, in the case of COD, the limitations imposed by Mie Theory itself. On the other hand, the Fractal Dimension (FD) has been used in the analysis of OCT images to examine the structural variations of biological tissues. In this study, we propose the use of fractal analysis to robustly and accurately estimate the size of scatterers as small as 0.1 μm in diameter. The box counting method was used to define the statistical characteristics of the FD, first calculated for individual neighborhoods and, subsequently, for the entire image. Using a prudently selected subset of these features, the scatterer size of microsphere phantoms was estimated with a mean error of 32.8 %. The proposed method will, of course, have to be tested further both on an expanded phantom set but also on human normal and disease tissue. However, given the preliminary results presented in this study, this approach has the potential to be further developed and to perform in vivo scatterer size estimation.

Keywords: Optical Coherence Tomography, Fractal Analysis, Scatterer Size

1. INTRODUCTION

The fact that a large proportion of early cancers arises in epithelia and exhibits variabilities in their cellular and subcellular microstructure has prompted much research effort towards measuring the size of optical scatterers in human tissues. Using spectroscopic OCT, the localized spectra that are inherently available in the OCT signal can be extracted [1, 2]. In the past, there have been various attempts to exploit these spectra to find metrics that can accurately measure the size of cell nuclei and other scatterers. One approach has been to curve-fit the backscattered spectra to the theoretical prediction curves [3-5]. Wax et al [6] further proposed pre-processing of the backscattered spectrum before the Fourier transform to improve the results. Another approach, proposed by Adler et al., relied on measuring the autocorrelation width of the spectrum [7, 8]. A more robust approach, based on the bandwidth of the correlation of the derivative (COD), has also been recently introduced [9]. However, these approaches are very challenging to apply to scatterer sizes below 3-4 μm due to their inherent lack of accuracy or, in the case of COD, the limitations imposed by Mie Theory itself.

Mandelbrot proposed fractal geometry and the concept of the fractal dimension (FD) in 1967 [10]. A FD is the ratio providing a statistical index of complexity when comparing how details in a pattern change with the scale at which the pattern is measured. Fluearu et al. utilized the box-counting method to calculate the FD for porcine arterial tissue characterization [11]. Sullivan et al. used the same technique for breast malignancy classification [12]. Furthermore, human skin studies reported that the FD could be used to discriminate melanomas from basal cell carcinomas and benign melanocytic nevi [13]. In ophthalmology, various researchers evaluated the fractal properties of the retinal vasculature to distinguish and diagnose eye diseases [14,15].

In this study, we propose the use of fractal analysis to robustly and accurately estimate the size of scatterers as small as 0.1 μm in diameter. The box counting method was used to define the statistical characteristics of the FD in the image and used those to estimate the scatterer size, thus filling a gap in the analysis and future clinical utilization of OCT imaging.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Phantom construction and image acquisition

The phantoms, used in this study, consisted of polystyrene microspheres embedded in a gelatin matrix. For the gelatin solution, 2g of gelatin powder were added to 40ml of water and was heated and stirred. Of that, 500 μ l were transferred to an Eppendorf tube and a volume (6.25, 12.5, 25, 50, or 100 μ l) of microspheres (diameters 0.1, 1, 2, or 4 μ m) was added and mixed. The tube was refrigerated for 5 hours, before thin slices of the gelatinous phantom were cut and imaged. The choice of microsphere concentrations was limited by the commercially available solutions but were chosen so that the phantoms would exhibit a range of comparable backscattering coefficients (Table 1).

Table 1. Microsphere concentrations and backscattering coefficients of the various phantoms.

Concentration	Microsphere Diameter							
	0.1 μ m		1 μ m		2 μ m		4 μ m	
	Spheres/ml	Backscat. μ (cm ⁻¹)	Spheres/ml	Backscat. μ (cm ⁻¹)	Spheres/ml	Backscat. μ (cm ⁻¹)	Spheres/ml	Backscat. μ (cm ⁻¹)
Low (L)	2.30 x 10 ¹²	0.078	1.18 x 10 ⁹	0.074	7.44 x 10 ⁷	0.058	9.30 x 10 ⁶	0.090
Medium (M)	4.60 x 10 ¹²	0.156	2.35 x 10 ⁹	0.148	1.49 x 10 ⁸	0.116	1.86 x 10 ⁷	0.179
High (H)	9.18 x 10 ¹²	0.312	4.70 x 10 ⁹	0.295	2.98 x 10 ⁸	0.233	3.72 x 10 ⁷	0.360

The OCT images were acquired using a swept source OCT system with a center wavelength of 1300 nm, an axial resolution of 10 μ m and an A-Scan rate of 40 kHz. Five images were collected from each of the 12 phantoms created, resulting in a total of 60 images. All the analysis was performed using Matlab.

2.2 Fractal and statistical analysis

Automated algorithms were developed to (i) segment the images and (ii) use the box-counting method to extract the statistics (mean, median, variance, standard deviation, kurtosis, skewness, sum, minimum, maximum) of the FD for each 15x15 pixel neighborhood of the image. The same statistics, but over the entire image, were subsequently calculated. The image mean intensity was also recorded resulting in 82 features for every phantom image.

2.3 Feature Selection and Scatterer Size estimation

Feature selection and optimization was performed in an effort to choose the features that result in the best estimation of the scatterer size. This process began with ranking the features using the minimum redundancy maximum relevance (MRMR) algorithm to identify the most statistically important ones. The feature set was further expanded to reduce the error of the scatterer size estimation. Eight features were finally utilized in the estimation processes, which included the mean intensity of the image as well as the image-wide mean, kurtosis and maximum of the [Mean FD], the variance of the [Median FD], the maximum of the [Sum FD], the minimum of the [Minimum FD], and the median of the [Maximum FD]. (The brackets are meant to signify the statistics at the neighborhood level.)

A 5th order linear equation we formulated to calculate the scatterer size:

$$SS = \mathcal{D} * Coeff = [D^0 D^1 D^2 D^3 D^4 D^5] * Coeff$$

where SS is the scatterer size, D are the features extracted from each image (60x(8x6) images x (features x orders)) and $Coeff$ is a matrix of coefficients (48 x 1) that yields the scatterer size. In a leave-one-out process, the coefficients of the equation were calculated from a training set that included all but one of the images, using the inverse of the data matrix:

$$Coeff = \mathcal{D}^{-1} * SS$$

The scatterer size of the remaining test image was estimated, using the calculated coefficients, and the process was repeated until all of the images were analyzed. The mean error in the scatterer size was calculated as an indicator of the effectiveness of the technique. The Student t-test was used to verify that the FD statistics and the scatterer sizes estimated were statistically different between phantom categories.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fig. 1A shows an example of an OCT image from a phantom with 2 μ m-diameter microspheres. A section of each such image was segmented (Fig 1A inset) and used to create a dataset (examples shown in Fig. 1B) for the fractal analysis. Fig.

2A shows the image-wide mean of the mean FD of each neighborhood. It is evident that there exists a relationship between the FD and scatterer size. However, this relationship is obscured by the fact that there are images of different microsphere densities, which alters the FD despite the fact that the scatterer size is the same in each case. Even so, the 4 different phantom categories are statistically different, with p-values much lower than 0.001. The estimation of the scatterer size, using the combination of features and the equations described above, also resulted in statistically different scatter size categories, and a mean error of 32.8 % in the estimation of the actual scatterer size (Fig. 2B).

Figure 1. (A) OCT image of a collagen/microsphere phantom with 2 μm diameter scatterers and a theoretical backscattering coefficient of 0.116 cm^{-1} . The green and red lines indicate the area automatically segmented for further processing, which is also separated in the inset. (B) Representative images of the 12 phantoms created for the purposes of this study. Their properties are summarized in Table 1.

Figure 2. (A) The mean over the entire image of the mean fractal dimension (FD) calculated from the OCT images of the collagen-microsphere phantoms. (B) The estimated vs. the actual scatterer size. The p-values, from the t-test, between categories are shown below.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a novel approach is presented which is uniquely suited for the estimation of the size of scatterers as small as 0.1 μm in diameter. The algorithm is using the statistics of the fractal dimension (FD), first calculated for individual neighborhoods and, subsequently, for the entire image. Using a prudently selected subset of these features, the scatterer size was estimated with a mean error of 32.8 %. The proposed approach must, of course, be further tested both on an expanded phantom set but also on human normal and disease tissue. However, the preliminary results presented in this study provide evidence that this approach has the potential to be further developed and to perform in vivo scatterer size

estimation, thus, providing a robust approach for the development of diagnostically useful biomarkers and the early diagnosis of disease.

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Clarification Note

Maria Fala performed the phantom imaging while an intern at the KIOS CoE. She is currently with the Cancer Research UK Cambridge Institute, Cambridge, United Kingdom

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